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CONTENTS

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES.....	51
<i>Mamadiev Elyor</i>	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE ESTABLISHMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILY GUEST HOUSES	55
<i>Boynazarov Ulugbek Egamberdievich</i>	
IMPROVING METHODS OF ORGANIZING AND DEVELOPING DOMESTIC TOURISM MARKETS IN UZBEKISTAN	61
<i>Daminov Mirvokhid Isroilovich</i>	
THE IMPACT AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR.....	67
<i>Dilsora Ibodovna Ibodova</i>	
IMPACT OF STUDENTS AGED OVER 40 ON ECONOMIC ACTIVITY AND BUDGETING BASED ON THE COMPETENCY ECOSYSTEM.....	74
<i>Nigora Ikrom qizi Primova</i>	
ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ: ЭКОНОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ И СЦЕНАРНОЕ ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ НА 2026–2030 ГОДЫ	80
<i>Юсупов Шерзодбек Бахтиёр угли</i>	
IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE PROCUREMENT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN COMMERCIAL ENTERPRISES.....	87
<i>Ergashev Jahongir Bakhodirovich</i>	
MULTIVARIATE ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING HOUSEHOLD INCOME IN SURXONDARYO REGION	93
<i>Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor qizi</i>	
СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЦИФРОВЫХ УСЛУГ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	99
<i>Юсифов Магамед Исмаил оглу, Гасанли Расул Шахин оглу, Белалова Гузаль Анваровна</i>	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MINING INDUSTRY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY.....	105
<i>Xudayberdiyeva Kamila Sadillovayna, Fozilova Zumrad Ahmadovna</i>	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF CLOTHING MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	111
<i>Axmedova Gaziza Azim kizi</i>	
КОМПЛЕКСНАЯ ОЦЕНКА ПОТЕНЦИАЛА РЕГИОНАЛЬНОГО АГРОПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО ИНТЕГРИРОВАНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ МОДЕЛИ АНР-TOPIS	115
<i>Аликулов А.Б.</i>	
APPLICATION OF CLUSTER METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE AND IMPROVEMENT OF ECONOMIC MECHANISMS IN SAMARKAND CITY	121
<i>Tashov Mizrob Maxmudovich</i>	
THE ROLE AND PROSPECTS OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN THE SERVICE SECTOR.....	130
<i>Musayeva Shoirazimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna</i>	
FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF REGIONAL ENTERPRISES	135
<i>Nigora Zokirjon qizi Toxirova</i>	
CURRENT STATE OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE METHODOLOGY OF ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY INDICATORS	142
<i>Temurbek Olimovich Mamayunusov</i>	
PRESUPPOSITION SHIFTS IN CROSS-LINGUISTIC RENDERING OF ANECDOTAL NARRATIVES: A COMPARATIVE INQUIRY INTO TRIGGER RETENTION AND TRANSFORMATION	148
<i>Umaraliyeva Dildora Taxirjanovna</i>	

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND RURAL PUBLIC SERVICE QUALITY: AN EMPIRICAL ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS.....	156
Bek Hunsia, Feruza Mansurovna Ollokulova	
COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF WOMEN'S LABOR ACTIVITY ON THE EFFICIENCY OF THE ECONOMIC SYSTEM.....	164
Ahrorova Asila Abduaziz qizi	
IMPROVING TAX ADMINISTRATION IN THE ENTREPRENEURIAL ENVIRONMENT.....	170
Azizbek Khurramov	
FORMATION OF FINANCIAL RESULTS AT MOTOR TRANSPORT ENTERPRISES.....	180
Shanazarova Nilufar Baratovna	
ARIMA-BASED ANALYSIS OF SMALL BUSINESS ACTIVITY IN THE AGRICULTURAL SECTOR OF SURKHANDARYA REGION.....	185
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
ASSESSMENT OF AGRARIAN SECTOR EFFICIENCY THROUGH THE SFA MODEL.....	192
Utanov Bunyod Kuvandikovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ ВНЕШНИМ ДОЛГОМ.....	196
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович, Жуманазаров Шахобиддин Дилмурод угли	
MODERN METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO MANAGING EDUCATIONAL SERVICES MARKETING IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	201
Shamshieva Nargizakhon Nosirkhuja kizi	
FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT OF FOREIGN AND DOMESTIC COTTON GINNING ENTERPRISES: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS, DIAGNOSTICS, AND IMPROVEMENT DIRECTIONS.....	208
Orif Jumayevich Murodov	
ANALYSIS OF THE INSTITUTIONAL FOUNDATIONS OF STATE INTERVENTION IN THE PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT PROCESS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	219
Atakulov Askad Raimkulovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ ФОРМАЛИЗАЦИИ НЕФОРМАЛЬНОЙ ЗАНЯТОСТИ И РАСШИРЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ ЗАЩИТЫ В АГРАРНЫХ РЕГИОНАХ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ КАШКАДАРЬИНСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ).....	224
Бобоназарова Юлдуз Ботировна	
THE ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF RESOURCE USE EFFICIENCY AND ITS ROLE IN INDUSTRIAL ECONOMICS.....	229
Baymanova Mavlyuda Djurayevna, Aipova Iroda Ikramovna	
THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM DEVELOPING COUNTRIES.....	234
Ismatova Diyora Sirojiddin qizi, Ubaydullayeva Gulchexra Erkabayevna	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ И РЕСУРСНАЯ АДАПТИВНОСТЬ ОТРАСЛИ МАШИНОСТРОЕНИЯ В РОССИИ, КИТАЕ, ИНДИИ.....	239
Викторова Наталья Геннадьевна, Абрамчикова Наталья Викторовна, Ван Байянь	
ENSURING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT.....	249
Aminova Naima Umar qizi	
STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH: PRACTICAL APPROACHES AND IMPROVEMENTS.....	253
Baymuradov Shokhrukh Makhmudovich, Dilmurodov Komiljon Ahmad o'g'li	
IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF SMALL ENTERPRISES IN THE SERVICE SECTOR (A CASE STUDY OF TASHKENT REGION).....	259
Ashirov Alisher	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN.....	264
Kurbanova Rahima Jamshedovna	
INNOVATIVE IDEAS OF YOUNG ENTREPRENEURS AND INFRASTRUCTURE FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL INNOVATIVE BUSINESSES.....	270
Ergashev Oybek Khaydaralievich	

MARKETING CHARACTERISTICS OF POSITIONING ORGANIC DRIED FRUIT PRODUCTS IN INTERNATIONAL MARKETS	274
Khidirov Shokhrukh	
TYPOLOGIZATION OF THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL AND DEVELOPMENT CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DISTRICTS OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON STATISTICAL AND NEURAL NETWORK APPROACHES.....	280
Normurodov Asliddin Alijon ugli	
THE ROLE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN ANALYSING THE THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE AUDIT OF FINANCIAL LIABILITIES	291
Palvanov Xusniddin Bekimmatovich	
DIGITAL SKILLS AND LABOUR PRODUCTIVITY: A SCENARIO ANALYSIS BASED ON AN INTEGRATED STATISTICAL MODEL	297
Madraimov Xabibulla Madaminovich	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ СТРУКТУРЫ АКТИВОВ И ПАССИВОВ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	303
Т.И. Бобакулов	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ ВНЕШНЕТОРГОВУЮ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ КОМПАНИЙ С ДОКУМЕНТАРНЫМИ АККРЕДИТИВАМИ	308
М.Т. Ибодуллаева	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ИНТЕГРИРОВАННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОСНОВНЫМИ СРЕДСТВАМИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	312
Мусаева Жамила Кароматовна	
ПРОБЛЕМНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	320
Ш.Т. Ибодуллаев	
THE IMPORTANCE OF STATE SUPPORT AND INVESTMENT POLICY IN ENSURING THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF MASS MEDIA ENTERPRISES.....	325
Sharipova Shahlo Istamovna	
CURRENT STATUS AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF MOTOR TRANSPORT SERVICES	329
Rakhimov Azamat Hamrakulovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ЭКСТРЕМАЛЬНЫХ МОДЕЛЕЙ В ОЦЕНКЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ.....	333
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна	
MULTI-FACTOR ECONOMETRIC MODELS OF WATER RESOURCE USE IN ENSURING REGIONAL ECONOMIC STABILITY.....	341
Xaitbaev Jasurbek Otaxanovich	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПРАКТИКИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ДОКУМЕНТООБОРОТА В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ.....	345
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович	
THE WAYS OF IMPROVING COMPETITIVENESS IN COMPANIES OF THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	350
Buriev Khakim Toshimovich, Usmanov Ixom Achilovich, Tolibov Abduazim Zoxid ugli	
MACROECONOMIC MODELS AND PROSPECTS OF TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	357
Sharipboyev Hasanboy Marks ugli, Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
THE IMPACT OF HRM PRACTICES ON ACADEMIC STAFF WORK EFFICIENCY IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	366
Sultonboyeva Munira Bahodirovna, Sultanova Kamila Muktorali Kizi	
THE ECONOMIC ROLE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	374
Inatullayeva Intizor Jamshid qizi	
ОЦЕНКА ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ КРУПНОГО РОГАТОГО СКОТА, ЗАВЕЗЁННОГО В РЕСПУБЛИКУ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН ИЗ-ЗА РУБЕЖА, С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ.....	378
Аскарова Нилуфар Бахтияровна	

COOPERATIVE MECHANISMS FOR REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT: A FRAMEWORK ANALYSIS OF CULTURAL TOURISM ENTERPRISE PARTNERSHIPS.....	382
Shohruxbek Ruziyev	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN METALLURGICAL ENTERPRISES: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND MODERN DEVELOPMENT TRENDS	393
Matkuliev Akbar Karimovich	
TAX INCENTIVES GRANTED TO ENTERPRISES LOCATED IN SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES	397
Torayeva Nafisa Odiljonovna	
REQUIREMENTS FOR TRANSITIONING TO ELECTRONIC BUSINESS AND CONDITIONS FOR DIGITALIZATION.....	402
Ismoilov Diyorbek Ismoiljon ugli	
DEVELOPMENT OF ALTERNATIVE ENERGY AS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR IN ENSURING A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY AND ENERGY SECURITY	407
Ergash Bobobekov	
ANALYSIS OF WAGE DYNAMICS IN THE EXAMPLE OF SURKHANDARYA REGION BASED ON PANEL DATA.....	412
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norquchqor kizi	
THE ROLE OF MARKETING STRATEGIES IN IMPROVING THE MARKET COMPETITIVENESS OF CARPET INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES	420
Arzieva Sevinch Shomurot kizi	
CONSUMER PROPERTIES OF FOOD PRODUCTS IN UZBEKISTAN: TRADITIONS, TRANSFORMATION AND NEW QUALITY STANDARDS.....	425
Gayrat Pardaev	
DIRECTIONS FOR STIMULATING ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH THE IMPROVEMENT OF THE TAX SYSTEM.....	431
Yakhshimuratova Khasiyat Khudaybergenovna	
THE ROLE OF E-COMMERCE IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS	435
Kambaraliyeva Intizor Suxrobovna	
Aliyarov Olim Abdug'aparovich	

THE ROLE OF E-COMMERCE IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS

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Abstract: The purpose of this article is to systematically analyze the role, dynamics, and development prospects of e-commerce in the economy of Uzbekistan in the context of digital transformation, as well as to develop practical proposals to increase sector efficiency. The relevance of the topic is determined by the need to modernize the national economy, simplify service delivery, and reduce the share of the shadow economy. As a personal approach of the author, the study evaluates the operations of local platforms like Uzum Market and Asaxiy in interconnection with regional logistics infrastructure. The scientific novelty lies in the comprehensive disclosure of mechanisms for increasing the export potential of small businesses and principles of strengthening cybersecurity through developing digital trade ecosystems in the republic. Based on the analysis, strategic recommendations were formulated to improve internet quality in remote areas and increase the digital literacy of the population. In conclusion, it has been proven that e-commerce is one of the main economic drivers that ensures GDP growth and creates new jobs. These proposals are of practical importance for improving the digital economy strategy.

Keywords: e-commerce, digital transformation, economic driver, digital trade ecosystem, local platforms, logistics infrastructure, cybersecurity, digital literacy, export potential.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolaning maqsadi raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida elektron tijoratning O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotidagi o'rnini, dinamikasi va rivojlanish istiqbollarini tizimli tahlil qilish hamda tarmoq samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha amaliy takliflar ishlab chiqishdan iborat. Mavzuning ahamiyati milliy iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiya qilish, xizmatlar ko'rsatishni soddalashtirish va yashirin iqtisodiyot ulushini qisqartirish zarurati bilan belgilanadi. Tadqiqotda muallifning shaxsiy yondashuvi sifatida Uzum Market, Asaxiy kabi mahalliy platformalar faoliyati va hududiy logistika infratuzilmasi o'zaro bog'liqlikda baholangan. Ilmiy yangiligi shundaki, respublikada raqamli savdo ekotizimlarini rivojlantirish orqali kichik biznes subyektlarining eksport salohiyatini oshirish mexanizmlari hamda kiberxavfsizlikni kuchaytirish tamoyillari kompleks ravishda ochib berilgan. Tahlillar natijasida chekka hududlarda internet sifatini yaxshilash va aholining raqamli savodxonligini oshirish bo'yicha strategik tavsiyalar shakllantirildi. Xulosa qilib aytganda, elektron tijorat mamlakat yalpi ichki mahsuloti o'sishini ta'minlovchi va yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratuvchi asosiy iqtisodiy drayverlardan biri ekanligi isbotlangan. Ushbu takliflar raqamli iqtisodiyot strategiyasini takomillashtirishda amaliy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli transformatsiya, iqtisodiy drayver, raqamli savdo ekotizimi, mahalliy platformalar, logistika infratuzilmasi, kiberxavfsizlik, raqamli savodxonlik, eksport salohiyati.

Аннотация: Целью данной статьи является системный анализ роли, динамики и перспектив развития электронной коммерции в экономике Узбекистана в условиях цифровой трансформации, а также разработка практических предложений по повышению эффективности сектора. Значимость темы определяется необходимостью модернизации национальной экономики, упрощения предоставления услуг и сокращения доли теневой экономики. В качестве личного подхода автора в исследовании взаимосвязанно оценивается деятельность местных платформ, таких как Uzum Market и Asaxiy,

с региональной логистической инфраструктурой. Научная новизна заключается в комплексном раскрытии механизмов повышения экспортного потенциала малого бизнеса и принципов укрепления кибербезопасности посредством развития экосистем цифровой торговли в республике. На основе анализа сформулированы стратегические рекомендации по улучшению качества интернета в отдаленных регионах и повышению цифровой грамотности населения. В заключение доказано, что электронная коммерция является одним из главных экономических драйверов, обеспечивающих рост ВВП и создание новых рабочих мест. Эти предложения имеют практическое значение для совершенствования стратегии цифровой экономики.

Ключевые слова: электронная коммерция, цифровая трансформация, экономический драйвер, экосистема цифровой торговли, местные платформы, логистическая инфраструктура, кибербезопасность, цифровая грамотность, экспортный потенциал.

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, the rapid development of information and communication technologies on a global scale has transformed traditional economic relations and led to the emergence of the e-commerce system, which represents the most dynamic component of the digital economy. Today, e-commerce has become one of the most effective tools for reducing business costs, expanding market reach, and providing consumers with fast and convenient services. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of the digital economy has also been identified as one of the priority directions of state policy. Within the framework of the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy, significant measures are being implemented to improve internet infrastructure and promote electronic payment systems.¹

In particular, the entry of local platforms such as Uzum Market, Asaxiy, and Olcha.uz into the market, along with the growing demand for online shopping among the population, further enhances the relevance of this research topic².

The object of this study is the modern e-commerce market of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including its infrastructure and digital economic relations. The subject of the study comprises the economic and organizational relationships associated with the patterns of e-commerce development, its contribution to economic growth, existing challenges, and prospective development models within the national economy.

The primary objective of this research is to evaluate the role and dynamics of e-commerce in the economy of Uzbekistan, identify the existing barriers in the sector, and develop a set of scientific and practical recommendations aimed at ensuring its sustainable development. To achieve this objective, the following tasks were defined and accomplished: examining the theoretical and methodological foundations of e-commerce development and international experience; conducting a statistical analysis of the current state and dynamics of the digital trade market in Uzbekistan; assessing the impact of e-commerce on employment, budget revenues, and the export potential of small business entities; identifying existing infrastructural, logistical, and legal challenges in the sector; and proposing solutions for improving the key drivers of e-commerce development in accordance with the economic conditions of the country.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The theoretical and practical aspects of e-commerce and digital economy relations have been extensively studied by numerous scholars at both the international and national levels. Among Western economists, Kenneth C. Laudon and Carol Guercio Traver, in their fundamental studies, analyzed e-commerce as a three-dimensional chain of interaction among business entities, technological infrastructure, and modern society. They paid particular attention to issues related to optimizing consumer behavior and global marketing strategies on online platforms. Another prominent international researcher, Efraim Turban, examined e-business models within the context of managerial efficiency and social network ecosystems, highlighting the role of online transactions in reducing corporate costs.

Furthermore, annual reports published by prestigious international institutions such as the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, the World Bank, and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development have systematically analyzed global digital transformation processes, cross-border data flows, and the macroeconomic factors influencing the development of the fintech sector in developing countries.

1 O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “Raqamli O‘zbekiston – 2030” strategiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida”gi Farmoni

2 O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Statistika agentligi va Markaziy bankingning rasmiy statistik hisobotlari ma’lumotlari.

In Uzbekistan, the formation of the e-commerce market and the prospects for digitalization have been reflected in the studies of local scholars and in major policy documents, particularly the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy and the Law “On Electronic Commerce.” Research conducted by domestic economists has primarily focused on establishing the legal and regulatory framework of the sector, ensuring the technical stability of national payment systems such as Uzcard and Humo, and developing electronic document management systems.

Unlike the studies conducted by both foreign and domestic scholars, the originality and novelty of the issue addressed by the author lie in the fact that e-commerce is examined not merely as a separate service sector, but as an integrated driver that enhances the export potential of small businesses and private entrepreneurship in the context of Uzbekistan's current economic growth and structural reforms. For the first time, the article comprehensively analyzes the rapid development of national marketplaces such as Uzum Market and Asaxiy in conjunction with regional logistics infrastructure, including fulfillment centers, and the level of digital literacy across different regions of the country.

In addition, the author provides a distinctive justification of the economic efficiency of models aimed at minimizing cybersecurity risks through the integration of artificial intelligence and Big Data technologies into local e-commerce systems as a means of overcoming traditional infrastructural barriers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The preparation of this article employed the methods of system analysis, comparative evaluation, economic-statistical grouping, induction, deduction, and synthesis. During the research process, official reports of the Statistics Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Central Bank, as well as statistical data from international organizations, were comparatively analyzed. The cost-reduction coefficient of e-commerce relative to traditional trade in the country was assessed using the grouping method. In addition, the growth dynamics of internet users and the volume of online transactions conducted through electronic payment systems such as Uzcard, Humo, Click, and Payme were compared, while logical analysis was applied to identify the key issues within the sector.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

This section constitutes the core part of the article, in which the share of e-commerce in the national economy and its economic efficiency were examined on the basis of statistical data. E-commerce enables businesses to reduce expenses associated with traditional store rentals, utility payments, and excessive staffing requirements. Marketing costs can also be optimized through internet-based advertising³.

The impact of e-commerce on economic growth is manifested, first, through increased employment opportunities in logistics, software development, and courier services; second, through the digitalization of trade operations, which contributes to reducing the shadow economy and increasing tax revenues to the state budget;⁴ second, through the digitalization of trade operations, which contributes to reducing the shadow economy and increasing tax revenues to the state budget; and third, through strengthening fair competition in the market and enhancing the export potential of domestic producers in foreign markets⁵. The key factors driving the dynamics of Uzbekistan's e-commerce market include the expansion of internet infrastructure and the simplification of online payments through Uzcard and Humo bank cards, as well as payment systems such as Click and Payme. At the same time, the rapid growth of the sector is creating new opportunities for the further development of e-commerce. In particular, substantial efforts are being undertaken to improve internet quality and speed in remote regions, enhance the population's digital literacy, and strengthen consumer confidence in online shopping⁶. Furthermore, considerable opportunities exist for enhancing cybersecurity measures, improving personal data protection systems, developing logistics networks for product delivery to remote districts, and continuously upgrading the regulatory and legal framework in line with modern requirements⁷.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This section concludes, based on the analysis and findings, that e-commerce is one of the most promising drivers of Uzbekistan's digital economic transformation. In order to address the identified challenges and further

3 Turban, E., Outland, J., King, D., Lee, J. K., Liang, T. P., & Turban, D. C. (2018). *Electronic Commerce: A Managerial and Social Networks Perspective*. Springer

4 World Bank. (2023). *Digital Development Overview: Connecting for Inclusion*. World Bank Group.

5 UNCTAD. (2021). *Digital Economy Report: Cross-border data flows and development*. United Nations.

6 OECD. (2024). *OECD Digital Economy Outlook*. OECD Publishing.

7 O'zbekiston Respublikasining “Elektron tijorat to'g'risida”gi Qonuni

accelerate the development of the sector, the following strategic measures are proposed: significantly expanding high-speed fiber-optic internet coverage across all remote regions of the country; introducing free educational programs aimed at improving digital literacy and cybersecurity awareness among citizens and entrepreneurs; strengthening legal mechanisms for the protection of users' personal and banking data; establishing modern logistics infrastructure and fulfillment centers throughout the republic; and providing tax and financial incentives to domestic e-commerce platforms while supporting their integration into international markets.

In the future, the widespread adoption of artificial intelligence and Big Data technologies within these systems will create opportunities to transform Uzbekistan into a major e-commerce hub in Central Asia.

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